

SIMUSAFE

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WHAT IS SIMUSAFE?

The acronym SIMUSAFE stands for SIMULATION of behavioural aspects for SAFER transport. The H2020 project will focus research on the most at-risk transportation situations by looking at dangerous road designs as well as the altered driving conditions that frequently impair road users.

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OBJECTIVE

SIMUSAFE aims to improve driving simulator and traffic simulation technology to more effectively and safely assess the risk perception and decision making of the following road user groups: Pedestrians, Bicycle riders, Motorcyclists and powered two-wheel riders, and Motor vehicle drivers.

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PARTNERS AND DATES

14 partners including both academic institutions and industry are taking part in the project. The project started 1 June 2017 and is expected to end 30 November 2020. For further information on partners and contributions please go to: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/723386>

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RESEARCH CYCLES

Three research cycles will be carried out aiming at a holistic verification of the initial data collected. The Field Operational Tests (FOT) have three distinct categories: Naturalistic Driving (ND), Controlled Environment (CE) and Simulation Driving Tests (SD).

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SIMULATORS

Partners are expected to carry out the research at various stages with four different simulator types utilising Unity software: car, bicycle, motorcycle and also pedestrian simulation.

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OUTCOME AND IMPACT

The project's expected outcomes will advance driver training programmes, the understanding of the usefulness of vehicle safety devices, and the safer integration of new types of vehicles, i.e. automated vehicles, on the roads. This aims to create a higher level socio-economic impact and outcome from the research.